

MASTERING WRITING SKILL IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Nurbekova Shakhnoza Sheralievna

English Teacher Institute of Textile and Light Industry

department of "Foreign languages"

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Annotation: This article discusses the causes and elimination of errors in a conversation in English.

Key words: English, speech, conversation, mistakes, purpose, letters, pronunciation.

Every year, the relevance of teaching writing and writing in English is increasing. This is due to the high degree of importance of knowledge of a foreign language in modern society. The practical significance of written verbal communication in the field of modern means of communication, such as e-mail, the Internet, in particular written communication with it, is great. The goal of an English teacher is to create the most suitable conditions for mastering writing skills. For this, in the learning process, it is necessary to solve problems that include the formation of students:

- graphic skills,
- speech-cognitive skills,
- the ability to formulate thoughts in accordance with the assignment, also written style,
- knowledge about the culture of the written work, its role,
- intellectual readiness to create the content of a written work,
- authentic ideas about the content of a written work. But, first of all, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of writing and written language. Written speech is defined as written speech, speech recorded on a letter, book style of speech.

That is, writing is a process of writing expressing thoughts. A letter is a text entry. The content of teaching writing at school includes several components. The first such component is graphics - the totality of all the means of a given writing. English uses Latin graphics. The English language graphics exist in two versions: printed and handwritten, each of which has in turn uppercase and lowercase letters, so almost every grapheme is represented by four variants of alphabetical units. Comparison of the font styles of printed and written fonts shows that some graphemes have close correspondences, while others print and handwritten variants differ sharply from each other. The difficulties of schoolchildren in mastering the grapheme-phonemic system of the English language find their expression in various graphic errors. The most typical of them are errors

associated with the insufficient distinguish between the faces of similar in English or in English and Russian languages due to the lack of clear differentiated patterns of the studied letters. So, students often interchange visually close graphemes b and d, d and g (often influenced by a similar Russian grapheme) and write besk, bress, gress, tadle, drass, do instead of desk, dress, table, grass, go.

The causes of errors often lie in the inability of students to distinguish in letters the spatial directions of similar elements. For example, the letters t, f, l, cause difficulties because they represent a long straight line. Students write face as tace and take as lake. Psychologically, this is because students find it easier to determine the similarity of different elements than the differences in similar elements; therefore, they quickly grasp similar elements of different letters and slowly distinguish between special, distinct from other elements of similar letters. A necessary exercise that focuses on the distinguishing features of these letters is a written speech exercise. Students experience difficulties in learning grapheme-phonemic correspondences in the English language, since there are no simple correspondences between graphemes and phonemes. One and the same phoneme can be expressed in different letters, letter combinations, the same letter can transmit different phonemes. For example, the letter "a" can transmit up to seven phonemes, the sound | f | can be conveyed by letters and letter combinations f, ph, ff, gh. The most frequent letter combinations require special attention and development. In order to form the skills of students in correctly writing the letters of the English alphabet and translating sounds and sound combinations into the corresponding letters and combinations, it is necessary to take into account: The similarity of the letters of the Russian and English alphabets; The interfering influence of the native language on the novelty of the letters of the English language; Variant of correspondence when translating English sounds into letters. The next component that makes up the content of teaching writing is spelling, which is defined as spelling or a system of rules for using written characters in writing specific words.

If the graphics allows for several options, then spelling is always used only one spelling to convey a certain word with this sound or sound combination, which is recognized as correct. One of the difficulties in spelling the English language is the discrepancy that exists between the sound of a word and the possible ways of its graphic representation. A striking example of such a discrepancy is, for example, the words right and write. Difficulties in English spelling are also determined by the fact that the alphanumeric and sound and letter spelling in the same words may not coincide, as a result of which it turns

out that in some cases it is simple to write a word, but difficult to read, and in others vice versa. For example, the words thin, this, them are simple to spell, and it seems difficult to read them. So, the alphanumeric correspondences for the digraph th are two-valued and nothing in the spelling of these words indicates the sonorous meaning of the digraph th, in some cases and the deaf - others. When teaching students should take into account the listed difficulties of spelling. To overcome them, to a certain extent, helps relying on certain principles: phonetic, morphological and traditional.

Since the possession of the letter is carried out through the assimilation of letters, words, phrases, sentences, over-phrasal unities, then each of the indicated units is the corresponding recording levels. The main value of recording at all levels is a deeper awareness of the features of the units of language and speech, and, therefore, their better memorization. However, recording can be an effective means of learning only if each written task is carried out in accordance with an appropriate educational task, stimulating the active mental activity of students. Thus, the writing of letters, words, accompanied by an analysis of their elements, create more durable graphic images and actualizes the meaning of lexical units. If before writing, as a form of speech activity, was not given much importance, now its role is not in doubt. Children themselves are convinced of this every day: they write letters to each other in a foreign language, exchange greeting cards, communicate using the computer networks of the Internet. But how to make the difficult and not always interesting stage of practicing spelling correct spelling words fascinating, interesting? Starting a new topic, the teacher in each lesson spends 5 minutes with a spelling task. The first stage is the initial presentation of vocabulary. Its purpose is to help students see which bricks words are made of. The second stage - re-presentation of vocabulary. Its purpose is to teach schoolchildren to isolate familiar words on a topic from many letters, to know how they are read, their meanings, and to be able to use them in new, already mastered speech patterns. The second stage includes 2 types of exercises. The first type of exercise is the "magic square". Students need to find, read, and translate the words in this square. The second type of exercise is to write as many sentences as possible with new words. The third stage. Its purpose is to carry out an intermediate control of spelling knowledge. Two types of exercises are offered. Exercise of the first kind: write the missing letters. Misspelled words are suggested. Exercise of the second kind: finish the words. Words are offered on the topic with two, three initial letters. The fourth stage. Its purpose is to check the degree of preparedness of students for the final control for spelling. Two types of

exercises are offered, which are designed for secondary students (exercises of the first kind) and well-performing (exercises of the second kind). The exercises are to make a word out of a set of letters. Seven letters are suggested and you must correctly spell a word of these seven letters. The fifth stage. Its purpose is to control knowledge of the spelling of new vocabulary. There can be two forms of control: if time is not a multi-vocabulary dictation, if enough, completing a crossword puzzle. Thus, the technology of teaching writing in English lessons usually includes two major aspects: work on the writing technique and the development of the ability to transmit semantic information using the graphic code of the language being studied, i.e. writing skills. The main task of the initial stage of training is to lay the foundations of the writing technique (i.e., to form calligraphic, graphic and spelling skills) through introducing students to writing letters, training in writing, spelling, spoken words, writing sentences containing learned.

Sources used:

1. Solovova E.N.. Methods of teaching foreign languages: Basic course / E. N. Solovova. - 3rd ed. - M.: AST: Astrel: Polygraphizdat, 2010
2. Konyshova A.V.. Modern methods of teaching the English language. - Minsk: TetraSystems, 2011
3. Biboletova M.Z.. Book for the teacher Enjoy English. - M, 2005
4. Simonova A.S., Khlebnikova E.A. Mastering the letter at the initial stage of teaching English // Young Scientist. - 2016

